

SUPPORTING DATA FOR THE FOLLOWING PAPER PUBLISHED
IN THE JOURNAL OF DAIRY SCIENCE

Invited review: Moving from dietary fat to fatty acids - New insights into how fatty acids impact digestibility, metabolism, and performance in dairy cows

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INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Invited review: Moving from Dietary Fat to Fatty Acids - New Insights into How Fatty Acids Impact Digestibility, Metabolism, and Performance in Dairy Cows. *By de Souza et al., page XXX.* Our objective was to review recent advances in our understanding of the role of individual fatty acids, focusing particularly on the impact of 16:0, 18:0, and 18:1 on nutrient digestibility, energy partitioning, and production responses of dairy cows. Overall, the review emphasizes the complexity of fatty acid digestion and metabolism, underscoring the need to tailor fatty acid supplementation strategies to the specific production stage and physiological status of dairy cows. The findings suggest future research should refine dietary formulations to optimize energy partitioning, improving productivity and metabolic health across lactation stages.

Supplementary Table S1. Descriptive statistics of variables in the data set used to run the random regression¹

Item	Overall			
	Mean	Min	Max	SD
DMI, kg/d	28.4	14.4	41.3	5.2
Nutrient digestibility, %				
DM	66.1	50.5	79.2	3.91
FA	75.1	9.66	90.7	8.35
NDF	42.4	17.4	63.3	6.9
FA intake, g/d				
16:0	343	25.0	953	178.0
18:0	40.7	3.51	254	34.5
18:1	184	23.7	347.2	56.9

¹Meta-regression of 19 studies conducted at Michigan State University with 1,449 individual cow observations. The model considered the random effect of study, cow within study and week/period within study and the fixed effect of FA intake on NDF digestibility. Equations were conducted initially using DMI and nutrients (as % DM) as independent variables and its interactions. Because we did not observe interactions, we decided to use intake of a given FA as independent variables. Predictions and interpretation did not change if using FA in % of DM or g/d.

Studies used:

- 1) Bales, A. M., J. M. dos Santos Neto, and A. L. Lock. 2024c. Effect of increasing dietary inclusion of whole cottonseed on nutrient digestibility and milk production of high-producing dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107(10):7798–7809.
- 2) Bales, A. M., J. de Souza, and A. L. Lock. 2025. Production responses are impacted by fatty acid profile rather than form of fat supplements in mid-lactation dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* (under review).
- 3) Benoit, A. C., J. M. dos Santos Neto, and A. L. Lock. 2024. Mammary gland responses to altering the supply of de novo fatty acid substrates and preformed fatty acids on the yields of milk components and milk fatty acids. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107:10653–10666.
- 4) Boerman, J. P., S. B. Plots, M. J. VandeHaar, and A. L. Lock. 2015b. Effects of partly replacing dietary starch with fiber and fat on milk production and energy partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98:7264–7276.
- 5) Burch, A. M., A. Pineda, and A. L. Lock. 2021. Effect of palmitic acid-enriched supplements containing stearic or oleic acid on nutrient digestibility and milk production of low- and high-producing dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104(8):8673–8684.

- 6) de Souza, J., and A. L. Lock. 2018a. Long-term palmitic acid supplementation interacts with parity in lactating dairy cows: Production responses, nutrient digestibility, and energy partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101(4):3044–3056.
- 7) de Souza, J., and A. L. Lock. 2019b. Milk production and nutrient digestibility responses to triglyceride or fatty acid supplements enriched in palmitic acid. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102:4155–4164.
- 8) de Souza, J., C. L. Preseault, and A. L. Lock. 2018. Altering the ratio of dietary palmitic, stearic, and oleic acids in diets with or without whole cottonseed affects nutrient digestibility, energy partitioning, and production responses of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101(1):172–185.
- 9) de Souza, J., C. Strieder-Barboza, G. A. Contreras, and A. L. Lock. 2019b. Effects of timing of palmitic acid supplementation during early lactation on nutrient digestibility, energy balance, and metabolism of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102(1):274–287.
- 10) de Souza, J., C. M. Prom, and A. L. Lock. 2021a. Altering the ratio of dietary palmitic and oleic acids affects nutrient digestibility, metabolism, and energy balance during the immediate postpartum in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104(3):2910–2923.
- 11) de Souza, J., J. L. Garver, C. L. Preseault, and A. L. Lock. 2017b. Short communication: Effects of prill size of a palmitic acid enriched fat supplement on the yield of milk and milk components, and nutrient digestibility of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100(1):379–384.
- 12) de Souza, J., N. R. St-Pierre, and A. L. Lock. 2019a. Altering the ratio of dietary 16:0 and cis-9 18:1 interacts with production level in dairy cows: Effects on production responses and energy partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102(11):9842–9856.
- 13) Liu, E., M. J. VandeHaar, and A. L. Lock. 2020. Effects of supplementing Holstein cows with soybean oil compared with palmitic acid-enriched triglycerides on milk production and nutrient partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103(9):8151–8160.
- 14) Parales-Girón, J., J. M. dos Santos Neto, and A. L. Lock. 2025. Whole cottonseed and palmitic and oleic acid supplementation improve production responses during the immediate postpartum in multiparous dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* (under review).
- 15) Pineda, A., J. de Souza, J. Newbold, R. M. Kirkland, and A. L. Lock. 2020. Effects of timing of a calcium salt supplement containing palmitic and oleic acids on production responses of early lactation dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* Vol. 103 (Suppl. 1): 69.
- 16) Prom, C. M., and A. L. Lock. 2021. Replacing stearic acid with oleic acid in supplemental fat blends improves fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104(9):9956–9966.
- 17) Rico, J. E., J. de Souza, M. S. Allen, and A. L. Lock. 2017. Nutrient digestibility and milk production responses to increasing levels of palmitic acid supplementation vary in cows receiving diets with or without whole cottonseed. *J. Anim. Sci.* 95(1):436–446.
- 18) Western, M. M., J. de Souza, and A. L. Lock. 2020a. Effects of commercially available palmitic and stearic acid supplements on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103(6):5131–5142.
- 19) Western, M. M., J. de Souza, and A. L. Lock. 2020b. Milk production responses to altering the dietary ratio of palmitic and oleic acids varies with production level in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103(12):11472–11482.

Supplementary Table S2. Descriptive statistics of variables in the data set used to run the random regression¹

Item	Overall			
	Mean	Min	Max	SD
Intake, g/d				
16:0	366	57.0	932	189
18:0	43.0	8.55	254	39.6
18:1	196	89.6	483.2	62.4
Energy output, Mcal/d				
Milk	33.1	17.3	45.9	5.31
Maintenance	13.7	11.1	17.5	0.97
Reserves	11.8	0.03	26.7	5.19
Energy partitioning, %				
Milk	56.7	42.8	78.6	6.52
Maintenance	23.7	17.0	36.5	3.01
Reserves	19.6	0.06	35.1	7.23

¹Meta-regression of 16 studies conducted at Michigan State University with 978 individual cow observations. The model considered the random effect of study, cow within study and week/period within study and the fixed effect of FA intake on NDF digestibility. Equations were conducted initially using DMI and nutrients (as % DM) as independent variables and its interactions. Because we did not observe interactions, we decided to use intake of a given FA as independent variables. Predictions and interpretation did not change if using FA in % of DM or g/d.

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- 2) Bales, A. M., J. de Souza, and A. L. Lock. 2025. Production responses are impacted by fatty acid profile rather than form of fat supplements in mid-lactation dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* (under review).
- 3) Benoit, A. C., J. M. dos Santos Neto, and A. L. Lock. 2024. Mammary gland responses to altering the supply of de novo fatty acid substrates and preformed fatty acids on the yields of milk components and milk fatty acids. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107:10653–10666.

- 4) Boerman, J. P., S. B. Plots, M. J. VandeHaar, and A. L. Lock. 2015b. Effects of partly replacing dietary starch with fiber and fat on milk production and energy partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98:7264–7276.
- 5) Burch, A. M., A. Pineda, and A. L. Lock. 2021. Effect of palmitic acid-enriched supplements containing stearic or oleic acid on nutrient digestibility and milk production of low- and high-producing dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104(8):8673–8684.
- 6) de Souza, J., and A. L. Lock. 2018a. Long-term palmitic acid supplementation interacts with parity in lactating dairy cows: Production responses, nutrient digestibility, and energy partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101(4):3044–3056.
- 7) de Souza, J., and A. L. Lock. 2019b. Milk production and nutrient digestibility responses to triglyceride or fatty acid supplements enriched in palmitic acid. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102:4155–4164.
- 8) de Souza, J., C. L. Preseault, and A. L. Lock. 2018. Altering the ratio of dietary palmitic, stearic, and oleic acids in diets with or without whole cottonseed affects nutrient digestibility, energy partitioning, and production responses of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101(1):172–185.
- 9) de Souza, J., J. L. Garver, C. L. Preseault, and A. L. Lock. 2017b. Short communication: Effects of prill size of a palmitic acid enriched fat supplement on the yield of milk and milk components, and nutrient digestibility of dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100(1):379–384.
- 10) de Souza, J., N. R. St-Pierre, and A. L. Lock. 2019a. Altering the ratio of dietary 16:0 and cis-9 18:1 interacts with production level in dairy cows: Effects on production responses and energy partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 102(11):9842–9856.
- 11) Liu, E., M. J. VandeHaar, and A. L. Lock. 2020. Effects of supplementing Holstein cows with soybean oil compared with palmitic acid-enriched triglycerides on milk production and nutrient partitioning. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103(9):8151–8160.
- 12) Pineda, A., J. de Souza, J. Newbold, R. M. Kirkland, and A. L. Lock. 2020. Effects of timing of a calcium salt supplement containing palmitic and oleic acids on production responses of early lactation dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* Vol. 103 (Suppl. 1): 69.
- 13) Prom, C. M., and A. L. Lock. 2021. Replacing stearic acid with oleic acid in supplemental fat blends improves fatty acid digestibility of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104(9):9956–9966.
- 14) Rico, J. E., J. de Souza, M. S. Allen, and A. L. Lock. 2017. Nutrient digestibility and milk production responses to increasing levels of palmitic acid supplementation vary in cows receiving diets with or without whole cottonseed. *J. Anim. Sci.* 95(1):436–446.
- 15) Western, M. M., J. de Souza, and A. L. Lock. 2020a. Effects of commercially available palmitic and stearic acid supplements on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103(6):5131–5142.
- 16) Western, M. M., J. de Souza, and A. L. Lock. 2020b. Milk production responses to altering the dietary ratio of palmitic and oleic acids varies with production level in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103(12):11472–11482.